

Fast loose rivet detection by using Scanning Laser Doppler Vibrometry

M. Stamm^{1,2}, S. Schlemme–Weber³, S. Appl³, J. Köser³, H. Pfeiffer²

¹ Brussels Airlines, Maintenance & Engineering,
Brussels Airport, Technical Complex South, Building 32, 1930 Zaventem, Belgium

² KU Leuven, Department of Materials Engineering,
Celestijnenlaan 300, B-3001, Heverlee, Belgium

³ Optomet GmbH,
Pfungstädter Straße 92, 64297 Darmstadt, Germany

Abstract

Until today, the manual inspection of riveted lab joints and detection of loose or damaged rivets is a time-consuming and costly task in the regular maintenance of civil aircraft. Many studies investigate the crack propagation in rivet holes or the influence of manufacturing parameters to the durability of riveted lab joints. However, no automated and digital in-situ quality assessment for loose and damaged rivets is explored so far. This work presents a study on a real aircraft fuselage panel in which Scanning Laser Doppler Vibrometer measurements enable the detection and distinction of loose, damaged and intact countersunk rivets.

On the one hand, a chirp sine excitation allows the detection of loose rivets by a coherence analysis of the excitation signal and the measured vibration. On the other hand, damaged and intact rivets appear in the vibration analysis as so-called local defect resonances at low and high frequencies respectively. The presented work potentially leads to a digital, automated and full-field inspection method suitable for the application in an industrial environment like the regular aircraft maintenance.

1 Introduction

Since the beginning of civil aviation, daily checks and regular maintenance of aircraft contribute significantly to the safety and reliability of air transport in general. One major aspect of aircraft maintenance are methods and procedures for non-destructive testing (NDT) which ensure the safe operation of critical parts and structural elements. Like in other sectors (e.g. inspection of buildings and bridges or nuclear power plants), novel NDT techniques are developed also in the aerospace sector as a result of the constantly increasing technical know-how and feasibility.

Despite the fact that aluminum is still widely used in aircraft structural parts, most novel NDT methods focus on the application on modern and lightweight materials like composite parts. However, according to a forecast by Airbus, 65 % of today's world fleet of 23000 will only be replaced until the year 2038 [1]. This explains the continuous need of NDT inspection methods also for "old-school" materials like aluminum.

One critical part of aircraft structures are the riveted lab joints of various components. Their fatigue behavior is explored in several numerical [2, 3] as well as experimental studies [4, 5] and can be found in many books like e.g. by Skorupa [6]. Even if riveted lab joints are well known for being a weak point in the aircraft structure, no automated and digital inspection method have been explored in the last decade.

Some articles like Riegert et al.[7] propose vibroacoustic thermography for the inspection of rivets and cracks in metal. Even if this approach seems promising, the method is based in the play between the two riveted metal sheets and does not grasp the play of each individual rivet. Another well established NDT inspection method which is widely used for the detection of surface cracks, is Eddy current. Le Diraison et al. [8] and

Lingvall and Stepinski [9] experiment with riveted lab joints where the focus lies on the subsurface crack detection in rivet holes. Besides the thermal and Eddy current inspection of aircraft components in general and specifically riveted lab joints, the application of a magneto–optic imaging technology is explored by e.g. Deng et al. [10] as well as Fan et al. [11].

However, in none of the aforementioned articles, the aspect of in–situ quality assessment of rivets and their connection to the surrounding structure is discussed. One method that is used since decades to characterize the vibrational behavior of various specimens and is successfully applied by Solodov et al. [12] to detect cracks in rivet holes, are measurements with Laser Doppler Vibrometers (LDV).

This work presents LDV measurements which enable the detection of loose and damaged rivets in a real aircraft fuselage panel.

2 Method

The principle of LDV measurements is based on the doppler shift which was first used by Davis and Kulczyk [13], who published their work in 1969 about a method to measure vibrations of a rotating bladed disc using a laser Doppler system. Since then, the technical development result in a constantly increasing signal–to–noise ratio. First concepts to scan a structure point–by–point were presented in 1980 [14]. The principle, history and major breakthroughs of LDV are summarized in various reviews and are beyond the scope of this paper [15, 16].

In this work, a Scanning Laser Doppler Vibrometer is used to record the surface vibrations of the aircraft fuselage panel which is excited with a broad band (typically chirp) signal by means of a piezoelectric patch. Analysing the vibrational response allows on the one hand the detection of uncoupled or badly coupled areas of the structure, being an indication for loose rivets. On the other hand, a chirp signal can excite some kind of local defect resonances (LDR) which originate from defects in the plate–like structure.

Following Solodov [17] a LDR results from the fact that the presence of a defect leads to a local decrease in stiffness of a certain mass of the material in the area of the LDR. Based on this definition, every rivet in a plate–like structure should give rise to a LDR as the rivet–plate connection will always have a stiffness lower than the stiffness of the surrounding plate. While many articles present the LDRs of flat bottom holes which come with a reduction of material thickness and stiffness in a certain area, rivets are usually thicker than the surrounding plate and add additional mass to the area while decreasing the stiffness. However, as both, the stiffness and the mass, influence the fundamental resonance frequency (f_0) of a LDR, the stiffness of a rivet–plate connection should affect the LDR center frequency, while the mass, being the same of defect and intact rivets, has no impact. Hence, the LDR frequency of a rivet in a plate–like structure gives an indication of the stiffness, or "tightness" of the rivet–plate connection.

This is true for rivets which are sufficiently coupled to the surrounding plate and which can be excited by the stimulating broad band signal. However, loose rivets with sufficient play in the rivet holes will not experience any defined excitation but shake "chaotically". This chaotic behavior can be quantified by calculating the coherence of two vibration signals which is done by e.g. Suryam et al. [18] for contact detection of two components. The coherence of the two signals, here the excitation and the vibrational response, is defined as

$$\text{COH}(\gamma^2) = \frac{S_{xy}(\omega)^2}{S_{xx}(\omega)S_{yy}(\omega)}, \quad (1)$$

where $S_{xx}(\omega)$ and $S_{yy}(\omega)$ are the two power spectral densities of the two signals $x(t)$ and $y(t)$ and $S_{xy}(\omega)$ their cross–power spectrum at an angular frequency ω . Suryam et al. also infer several properties of which the most important for this work is that the coherence is close to unity for a linear correlation between the vibrational signal and the input excitation. This can be used to identify loose rivets as areas of low coherence, whereas other parts of the specimen that are properly coupled to the excitation source are characterized by a coherence value of nearly one. The coherence is hence used as a statistical measure for the mechanical coupling between the rivet and the surrounding structure. To estimate a single scalar value for COH, which is generally frequency dependent, it is convenient to calculate the *root–mean–square* of COH, COH_{RMS} .

2.1 Measurements

The measurements presented below are performed on a real aircraft fuselage panel from a Airbus A320. The panel is made from aluminum (AL 2024-T3) and coated with a primer and conventional aircraft paint. In the panel, a service door mounted which allows quick access to a underlying pressure release valve which is used in the daily maintenance of the aircraft. The opening for this door is surrounded by a supporting frame which is riveted with countersunk rivets to the plate. This setting is an ideal example of riveted lab joint in an aircraft fuselage panel and serves the demonstration of the proposed methods to detect loose and sheared rivets.

Figure 1: The two areas of a fuselage panel from an Airbus A320 aircraft with modified rivets which are measured in this study. The two images at the top show area I from the front (top) and the back side of the panel (middle). The bottom image shows the screws holding the door hinge, of which one (right screw) has a loose nut and is hit once with a hammer from the back.

For this study, two areas of the panel are modified and measured with a Optomet's Scanning Laser Doppler Vibrometer. One area ("area I") is a row of countersunk rivets of which one rivet is heavily hammered to loose it and another rivet is slightly modified by rotating it with pliers. The play of the loose rivet is so big that it is possible to rotate the rivet with bare handed. The second rivet is still tight but obviously modified from the back. In Figure 1, the two top images show area I and the loose rivet (fourth from the left) as well as the slightly modified rivet (second from right) are easy to recognize from the back side of the panel. All other rivets in that row are not intentionally modified, but experienced some stress due to the surrounding work on the loose rivet. The second area ("area II") is a row of five countersunk screws which hold the door hinges. The bottom image in Figure 1 shows area II where the screw at the very right has a loose nut and is hammered once from the backside to generate a small play between screw and plate.

The measurements are performed with a compact Scanning Laser Doppler vibrometer from Optomet GmbH. This scanning head has an integrated function generator which simplifies the experimental setup as there is no need to synchronize the excitation signal and data acquisition externally. With 1550 nm, this SLDV

operates in the *short-wave infrared (SWIR)* range which allows an output power of 10 mW while it still falls under Laser protection class 1. This is especially important for the operation in an industrial environment like aircraft hangars. The scanning head has an operating angle of 40° by 50° and an in-built Full HD camera for a later mapping of the measured points to the real photo on the sample under test [19]. To generate a sufficient excitation, a piezoelectric driver is used to amplify the signal provided by the internal function generator and drives the piezoelectric patch (PZT). A sketch of the experimental setup is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: A sketch of the experimental setup which includes the SLDV head (blue), the voltage amplifier (black and the fuselage panel with the attach PZT patch (gray and yellow).

The excitation signal which drives the PZT is a $\tau = 23$ ms long sine chirp signal from 1 kHz to 350 kHz. To further reduce the noise, for every point in the measurement grid, three measurements are performed. For the post-processing, the single measurement as well as the averaged time signal can be used. In this work, the analysis is solely based on the averaged signals.

3 Results

To visualize the vibration behavior of the specimen in a single image, the *root mean square (RMS)* is calculated in the frequency domain for every measurement point. For this, the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) of each point is exported from the measurement software (OptoScan) and band-pass filtered before the RMS is calculated and normalized to one. Together with an adapted colormap for the visualization, a good feature extraction for various frequency ranges is achieved. The colormap is tailored to each frequency band so that the lowest 0.8 % of measurement points are shown red and the highest 0.5 % of measurement points are in saturation.

The coherence map and the RMS for different frequency ranges of area I are shown in figure 3. At the top, the RMS of the coherence is shown where all points below the threshold of $\text{COH}_{\text{RMS}} < 0.8$ are red. The four middle plots (b)-(e) show the RMS of measured signals for different frequency bands with constant band widths (50 kHz). At the bottom (e), the unfiltered RMS and the corresponding colormap is shown.

Figure 3: The coherence analysis (a) and band pass filtered and normalized RMS for different frequencies for area I of the fuselage panel. The color bar at the bottom refers only to (d) as it is adapted for each filter according to the description above.

A close-up of the damaged but tight rivet (fourth rivet from the right) is shown in figure 4 for different frequencies. The different pattern correspond to the different vibrational modes of the system with a fundamental frequency 25(1) kHz and higher harmonics at 51 kHz, 76 kHz, 89 kHz, 125 kHz and 169 kHz.

Figure 4: Different vibration modes of the middle left rivet (area I) for the fundamental frequency (a) 25(1) kHz and higher harmonics (b-f) 51 kHz, 76 kHz, 89 kHz, 125 kHz and 169 kHz. Additional vibration pattern are shown in Appendix A.

In figure 5, the measurement of area II is shown. The top three plots show the RMS data for different band-pass filters (a) 15 kHz to 65 kHz, (b) 115 kHz to 165 kHz, (c) 260 kHz to 310 kHz. The bottom plot (d) shows the unfiltered data and the corresponding colorbar which is, as described above, different for the other plots as it changes from image to image.

Figure 5: The band pass filtered and normalized RMS heat map for different frequencies for area I of the fuselage panel. The color bar at the bottom refers only to d) as it is adapted for each filter according to the description above.

4 Discussion

The measurements in figure 3 and 5 show the feasibility to detect loose and damaged rivets and screws with SLDV measurements. In both cases, the modified fastener have a different signature than the other intact fastener.

4.1 Area I

In area I, two different behavior of modified rivets are found. On the one hand, the loose rivet that is freely moving in its rivet hole appears in the analysis of the coherence as well as in the RMS of the vibration. Both physical interpretations of the measurement data indicate the bad coupling of the rivet to the surrounding plate. The non-linear vibration of the rivet due to the play between plate and rivet result in a low coherence between input signal and measured vibration. One advantage of this analysis technique is that the distinction between a loose rivet or bolt and vibrational good coupled areas is very clear. In figure 6, shows the histogram of all COH_{RMS} values in area I and the threshold of $\text{THD} = 0.8$ which separates red and green or "good" and "bad" measurement points. However, as seen in figure 3, the analysis of the coherence is not suitable to detect damaged but tight rivets. For this, an analysis of the frequency-dependent vibration is required.

As seen in figure 3, loose as well as damaged rivets can be detected by analyzing the frequency-dependent vibration of the rivets. In principle, two behaviors should be distinguished. As the analysis is based on the average of three measured time signals, a "chaotic" and non-linear vibration with respect to the input signal by e.g. a loose rivet result in a low RMS value. This is true for the full frequency spectrum analyzed in this work and the loose rivet appears in red for all frequency-bands shown in 3.

Damaged rivets that are well coupled to the surrounding plate do show up in the vibration analysis due to the excitation of different resonances of the plate-rivet system. In figure 3 (b) and (c), two excited rivets are visible at different frequencies. Figure 4 confirms that the damaged rivet appear as a LDR when the excitation frequency meets one local harmonic of the rivet-plate system. The lowest frequency at which the rivet shows a resonant behavior is $f_0 = 25$ kHz, followed by 51 kHz, 76 kHz, 89 kHz, 125 kHz and 169 kHz. The pattern are similar to the vibration pattern of a plate-like structure at harmonics that are multiples of the fundamental patterns and are measured by e.g. Segers et al. for flat-bottom holes[20]. With some

Figure 6: Histogram of all COH_{RMS} values in area I indicated in green if above the threshold and red if below the threshold of $\text{THD} = 0.8$.

uncertainty, the pattern appear at $1f_0$, $2f_0$, $3f_0$, $5f_0$. For a linear system, one would expect the fourth harmonic at $4f_0 = 100$ kHz and not at 89 kHz as shown in figure 4d. The same holds for the harmonic in $4f$ which is visible at 169 kHz instead of $6f_0 = 150$ kHz or $7f_0 = 175$ kHz. However, it can be said that the rivet appears in the vibrational analysis for many more frequencies and with different vibration pattern of which some are shown in Appendix A.

Despite this offset in expected harmonic frequency, the measurement of vibration pattern is an impressive confirmation for the assumption that the rivet–plate system act like LDRs that are conventionally investigated in a plate structure with cracks, delaminations or flat bottom holes.

Besides the damaged rivets that appear as LDRs, another feature can be detected in figure 3 (d) between 10 cm to 15 cm. This resonances with a shape of four horizontal stripes might indicate a faulty area in the sealing between the two riveted plates. It is common practice that riveted lab joints are sealed with some grease similar to silicone which is spread between the two riveted plates. When the sealant is spread with a comb to ensure a equal distribution, a stripe–like structure as seen in figure 3 (d) might occur and show up as a vibration pattern when excited with the right frequency. A close look at 3 (b) already indicate this area as a single local resonance in which the wavelength too long to resolve the different stripes.

Figure 3 (e) refers to the vibration pattern for 280 kHz to 330 kHz and shows that also tight and intact rivets show up as local resonances at high frequencies. This is especially interesting as only the intact rivets are visible and the two damaged rivets are almost invisible. Other than the damaged rivets, the intact rivets appear as rings and the vibration is restricted to the outer corner of the rivet where the weak spot between surrounding plate and rivet result in an excited vibration. Both aspects are of utmost importance as they enable the detection of intact rivets which, if not detected at low frequencies, can be classified as healthy.

4.2 Area II

In area II, the screw with the loose nut is clearly visible in the RMS and shows a different behavior than the tight screws. Figure 5 (a) and (b) shows the low frequency band–pass filtered RMS where the loose screw is clearly visible. Even if the screw head has a shape far more complex than of a plate, like for the damaged rivet, different vibration modes with resonances at different regions can be seen. While 5 (a) indicates a vibration of the inner part of the screw, 5 (b) visualizes the outer as well as inner edge of the screw head. For high frequencies above 250 kHz, the same behavior as for area I can be demonstrated in 3 (c) where all screw heads appear as local resonances. In addition to the screws, a intact rivet at the very right of the measurement area appears and confirms that intact rivets are detectable at high frequencies (>250 kHz).

For a concise visualization, the same colormap as for area I is used to show area II. However, as this area contains no loose parts and all measured points show a high coherence between input signal and measured vibration, the red pixel corresponding to the lowest 0.8% RMS are not clustered and do not provide any information to be interpreted.

5 Outlook

The presented measurements demonstrate the feasibility to detect and differentiate between loose, damaged and intact rivets in aircraft fuselage panels. As this work is conducted on a real aircraft panel, technically the measurements can easily be transferred and used in the in-line maintenance in the hangar or even on the runway. However, as described above, the PZT batches have been glued on the fuselage panel for this study. For obvious reasons this is not possible in the daily aircraft maintenance as the effort of removing the PZT would outweigh the benefits of a digital and automatized inspection method. However, in other studies by e.g. Segers et al., the PZT was glued on the specimen by phenyl salicylate which melts at 45 °C and enables the easy removal of the PZT after the measurement [20, 21].

For an application in an industrial environment, an automated post-processing and rivet evaluation is required. The presented data indicate the multidimensional nature of rivet inspection with SLDV which result in feature extraction for different frequencies and analysis methods (RMS vs. COH). For a automated or semi-automated evaluation of rivets, all parameters have to be taken into account and should result in a single and easy to interpret output image which indicates intact, damaged and loose rivets. A possible output of an automated rivet quantification could look like shown in figure 7.

Figure 7: An automated rivet detection and quantification should combine different parameters and result in a single, easy to interpret image.

6 Conclusion

The presented work demonstrates the feasibility to identify loose, damaged and intact rivets in riveted lab joints of aircraft fuselage panels with Ultrasound excited SLDV measurements. The specimen being a real aircraft fuselage panel with loose and damaged rivets and screws serves as a good test sample on which realistic conditions for later applications are found.

The results indicate that rivets with different tightness in the surrounding plate show different vibrational behaviors in the investigated frequency band of 1 kHz to 350 kHz and can potentially be categorized in three groups being intact rivets, loose rivets and damaged rivets. The results of this study might lead towards a

automated and fully digital measurement system which detects and characterizes loose, damaged and intact rivets and bolts in aircraft fuselage panels.

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A Vibration pattern

